

SHORT NOTES

Preparation of Some α -Bromo-1-(subst. phenyl)-1,3-buta-diones

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In continuation of the earlier work (Garg, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 36, 948) on the bromination of reactive methylene compounds through their sodium or copper salts, the bromination of 1-phenyl-1,3-buta-diones has now been studied. These diones can yield two bromo compounds (I & II):

It has been shown by previous workers (Kröhnke and Timmler, *Ber.*, 1936, 69B, 614) that (I) is converted to (II) in presence of hydrobromic acid. The present method has the advantage that no free hydrobromic acid is formed in the course of the reaction so that there is no possibility of interconversion. In all these cases only the 2-bromo compounds (I) were formed.

The bromine atom is very labile and the bromo compounds liberate iodine from acidified potassium iodide solution resulting in the original β -diketones.

Sodium Salts of 1-(Subst. phenyl)-1,3-buta-diones.—A mixture of ethyl acetate (1 mol.), substituted acetophenones (1 mol.), ether, and granulated sodium (1 atom) was kept at 0° for several days. The sodium salts thus obtained were filtered and washed well with dried ether.

Copper Salts of β -Diketones.—Sodio-derivatives obtained above were treated with ice-cold dilute acetic acid and the liberated β -diketones taken up in ether. On prolonged shaking of the extracts with aqueous cupric acetate, the copper complexes, which precipitated, were crystallised from chloroform.

2-Bromo-1-(subst. phenyl)-1,3-buta-diones.—The sodium or copper salts of β -diketone were suspended in CCl_4 , cooled, and then treated with bromine (mol. ratio), dissolved in the same solvent. The metallic bromides formed were filtered. The residues left after evaporation gave the bromo derivatives. These were recrystallised from alcohol. The bromo derivatives thus obtained are described in Table I.

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TABLE I

No.	X.	X'	% Yield.		M.P.*	Colour.	Formula.	% Halogen:	
			Na salt.	Cu salt.				Found.	Calc.
1	Cl	H	54	61	54°	Colorless	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ BrCl	41.80%	41.90%
2	Br	H	77	63	68	Colorless	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ Br ₂	49.67	50.00
3	CH ₃	H	56	61	64	Colorless	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ Br ₂	30.76	31.37
4	Cl	Cl	58	60	51	Colorless	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₂ BrCl ₂	48.60	48.70
5	CH ₃ O	H	58	60	39	Dirty white	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br	29.20	29.50

*M.P.s. are uncorrected.

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